

Effect of Flaying Capacitors on Improving the 4 Level Three-Cell Inverter

Kelaiaia Mounia Samira, Labar Hocine, Bounaya Kamel, and Kelaiaia Samia

Abstract—With the rapid advanced of technology, the industrial processes become increasingly demanding, from the point of view, power quality and controllability. The advent of multi levels inverters responds partially to these requirements. But actually, the new generation of multi-cells inverters permits to reach more performances, since, it offers more voltage levels. The disadvantage in the increase of voltage levels by the number of cells in cascades is on account of series igbts synchronisation loss, from where, a limitation of cells in cascade to 4. Regarding to these constraints, a new topology is proposed in this paper, which increases the voltage levels of the three-cell inverter from 4 to 8; with the same number of igbts, and using less stored energy in the flaying capacitors. The details of operation and modelling of this new inverter structure are also presented, then tested thanks to a three phase induction motor.

Keywords—Flaying capacitors, Multi-cells inverter, pwm, switchers, modelling.

I. INTRODUCTION

THE important development which touched the technology of semiconductors [1] opens new research orientations, particularly in the energy conversion techniques. Like first step of development, one can cites the integration of inverters with multi levels NPC structures in electrical power systems [2]. The field of application of these inverters is very varied: control of electrical energy conversion in the industry [3], transmission power system stability (FACTS) [4, 5], and improvement of power quality in the networks by active filters [6], renewable energies interfaces [7-10], etc... Also they are an interesting alternative for medium and high power drives [11], because the control of this type of motors by the traditional techniques is on the one hand very delicate, and on the other hand, generates disturbances in the neighbouring network of which they are connected. One of the strong points of multi levels structure is its soft adjustment [3]. The new inverters generation is actually the multi-cells ones. The invention of this type of inverter is likely to discredit the traditional multi-level inverter, because, they offer a better performance with more flexibility, low cost and commutations [12]. Several researchers studied these new structures, from the

point of view: topological [13], comparative with the other existing structures [14], techniques of controls [12], insertion in the power grid [12], etc...

II. MULTI-CELLS STRUCTURE

The multi-cell inverter is designed by the connection of cells in cascade Fig. 1, separated by capacities operating in series [15]. The alternating voltage which feeds load is obtained via an artificial neutral (N), taken at the medium point of the DC source (E). The operation of this inverter can be grouped on the Table I, in which one presents all the possible sequences of commutations offered by switchers SW .

Fig. 1 Three cells inverter Structure

TABLE I
 INVERTER OPERATION

	SW_1	SW_2	SW_3	V_{PG}	V_{PN}
V_1	up	up	up	E	$E/2$
V_2	up	up	down	$E - V_{C1}$	$E/2 - V_{C1}$
V_3	up	down	up	$E - V_{C2} + V_{C1}$	$E/2 - V_{C2} + V_{C1}$
V_4	up	down	down	$E - V_{C2}$	$E/2 - V_{C2}$
V_5	down	up	up	V_{C2}	$V_{C2} - E/2$
V_6	down	up	down	$V_{C2} - V_{C1}$	$V_{C2} - V_{C1} - E/2$
V_7	down	down	up	V_{C1}	$V_{C1} - E/2$
V_8	down	down	down	0	$-E/2$

The function of switchers is to allow the passage through all possible voltage levels V_k ; $K \in [1 \div 8]$. Against, the diodes are used to make a stress distribution at the flaying capacitors, during the micro phases of switchers break time, thus allowing, maintaining their voltages around a fixed value.

M.S. Kelaiaia is with Department of Electrical Engineering, Faculty of Engineering Sciences, University of Annaba; B.P. 12, 23000, Algeria (phone/fax 213 3887 5398; e-mail: kelaiaiams@yahoo.fr)

H. Labar: is with Department of Electrical Engineering, Faculty of Engineering Sciences, University of Annaba; B.P. 12, 23000, Algeria (e-mail: Hocine.Labar@univ-annaba.org)

K. Bounaya is with Department of Electrical Engineering, Faculty of Engineering Sciences, University of Guelma, Algeria (e-mail: bounayak@yahoo.fr).

S. Kelaiaia is with Department of Electrical Engineering, University of Souk Ahras; Algeria (e-mail: samiakelaiaia@yahoo.fr).

Fig. 2 Flying capacitors distribution voltages

As the diodes are identical, they present then, the same voltage drops, so, this results to write: $E = 6\Delta U_D \Rightarrow \Delta U_D = E/6$. The diode voltage drop (ΔU_D) will impose at the flying capacitors the voltages $V_{C1} = E/3$ (see circuit 2, P, 2'), & $V_{C2} = 2E/3$ (see circuit 1, 2, P, 2', 1') Fig. 2. Thus, in accordance with these two values of V_{C1} and V_{C2} , one notices that this inverter offers 4 level voltages $V_{PN} = [E/2 \ E/6 \ -E/6 \ -E/2]$; Table I.

With an aim of generalization, and so that this study will not be limited to an inverter with 3 cells, a relation which gives the terminal flying capacitors voltage for an inverter with n cells is defined Fig. 3.

Fig. 3 Multi-cells structure

The voltage of each diode $\Delta U_D = E/n$, so one can define the terminal voltages of flying capacitors $V_{C(n-k)} = (n-2k).E/n$

Let us study more in detail the inverter with 3 cells. The voltage V_{PG} is the sum of each cell voltage (1). They even depend on the conduction state of switchers' (Fig. 1).

Phase to ground voltage

$$V_{PG} = V_{Cell1} + V_{Cell2} + V_{Cell3} \quad (1)$$

Cells voltages

$$V_{Cell3} = \begin{cases} E & \text{if } SW_3^{up} \\ -E & \text{if } SW_3^{down} \end{cases}$$

$$V_{Cell2} = \begin{cases} -V_{C2} & \text{if } SW_3^{up} \ \& \ SW_2^{down} \\ 0 & \text{if } SW_3^{up} \ \& \ SW_2^{up} \\ 0 & \text{if } SW_3^{down} \ \& \ SW_2^{down} \\ V_{C2} & \text{if } SW_3^{down} \ \& \ SW_2^{up} \end{cases}$$

$$V_{Cell1} = \begin{cases} -V_{C1} & \text{if } SW_2^{up} \ \& \ SW_1^{down} \\ 0 & \text{if } SW_2^{up} \ \& \ SW_1^{up} \\ 0 & \text{if } SW_2^{down} \ \& \ SW_1^{down} \\ V_{C1} & \text{if } SW_2^{down} \ \& \ SW_1^{up} \end{cases}$$

Since the switchers of the same cell must be complementary, in order to avoid the open circuits or the parallel connection of two various values of voltages. Then, if one of the switchers is at the state on, the other one must be at the state off. Thus in number language, it is proposed, for the switcher up SW^{up} "1" and for the switcher down SW^{down} "- 1" Table II. This made, and in accordance with the system (2) we define the switching functions for each cell.

$$V_{Cell3} = (1 + SW_3).E/2$$

$$V_{Cell2} = (SW_2 - SW_3).E/3$$

$$V_{Cell1} = (SW_1 - SW_2).E/6$$

$$V_{PN} = V_{PG} - E/2$$

After replacement of these last expressions in the relation (1), one finds: $V_{PG} = (3 + SW_3 + SW_2 + SW_1).E/6$

The fact of having the same voltage for various sequences of commutations can be used in the loop of control, like additional degree of freedom for the voltage maintaining of each capacitors to its fixed value [15]. In order to pass through all the sequences (Table II) same authors propose 3 carriers shifted to 1/3 of period each [16] (Fig. 4). The control technique presented is the pulse wide modulation PWM, with triangular carriers.

Fig. 4 Three carriers and the corresponding output voltage

Fig. 5 Simulation model

(a)

(b)

Fig. 6 Harmonics Spectrum
 (a) Voltage
 (b) Current

TABLE II
FLAYING CAPACITORS EFFECT

C μ F	20	25	30	35	40	45	50	55	60
THD _v %	4.3649	3.5388	3.0069	1.2744	2.3764	1.9133	1.8207	1.7461	1.6839
V _{OutPut}	145.23	145.34	145.41	145.66	145.48	145.54	145.55	145.56	145.57
THD _I %	1.8968	1.5995	1.4195	0.9759	1.2241	1.0967	1.0733	1.0564	1.0419
I _L	14.52	14.53	14.54	14.56	14.54	14.55	14.556	14.55	14.55

III. SIMULATION AND RESULTS

The single phase multi-cell inverter is modelled then simulated for a fixed RL load “R=10 Ω & L=1.5mH” with different Flaying Capacitors values.

Varying the capacitor on can notice a clear improvement of the output variables and the power quality delivered by the inverter. This says the optimization of the capacitors sizes used make it possible to reach the best performances of the multi-cellular inverter:

- A great stability of intermediate voltages V_{C1} and V_{C2}.
- The THD_v and THD_I are on their low level respectively 1.2744% and 0.9759% .
- All the energy of the DC bus is transferred towards the alternate consumer as a fundamental frequency with a minimum energy waste, evaluated to 2.93%.

Fig. 7 Effect of capacitors sizes on the distributed voltages

IV. CONCLUSION

The wished inverter output voltage defined by the reference is an average value between successive levels commutations, in an interval time fixed by carrier period. This voltage sample influences the sinusoid current thickness, because the commutation from one level to another imposes important electromagnetic energies exchange stored in the reactive elements. This unwanted exchange can be attenuated by the optimal choice of the Flaying Capacitors values.

REFERENCES

[1] Pérez-tomás, x. Jordà, p. Godignon, j. L. Gálvez, m. Vellvehí and j. Millán igt gate driver ic with full-bridge output stage using a modified standard cmos process *microelectronics journal*, volume 35, issue 8, august 2004, pages 659-666.

[2] Said barkati, lotfi baghli, el madjid berkouk and mohamed-seghir boucherit harmonic elimination in diode-clamped multilevel inverter using evolutionary algorithms electric power systems research volume 78, issue 10, october 2008, pages 1736-1746.

[3] J. Rodriguez, j.-s. Lai, and f. Z. Peng, “multilevel inverters: a survey of topologies, controls, and applications,” *iee trans. Ind. Electron.*, vol. 49, no. 4, pp. 724–738, aug. 2002.

[4] X. Xu, y. Zou, k. Ding, and f. Liu, “cascade multilevel inverter with phase-shift spwm and its application in statcom,” in *proc. Ieee icon*, 2004, pp. 1139–1143.

[5] J. N. Chiasson, l. M. Tolbert, k. J. Mckenzie, and z. Du, “elimination of harmonics in a multilevel converter using the theory of symmetric polynomials and resultants,” *iee trans. Control syst. Technol.*, vol. 13, no. 2, pp. 216–223, mar. 2005.

[6] defay, f.; llor, a.m.; fadel, m.a direct predictive control of shunt active power filters using multicell converter, 2007 european conference on power electronics and applications volume , issue , 2-5 sept. 2007 pp:1 – 9.

[7] J. M. Carrasco, l. G. Franquelo, j. T. Bialasiewicz, e. Galvan, r. C. Portilloiguisado, m. A. M. Prats, j. I. Leon, and n.moreno-alfonso, “power-electronic systems for the grid integration of renewable energysources: a survey,” *iee trans. Ind. Electron.*, vol. 53, no. 4, pp. 1002– 1016, jun. 2006.

[8] H. Ertl, j. W. Kolar, and f. C. Zach, “a novel multicell dc-ac converter for applications in renewable energy systems,” *iee trans. Ind. Electron.*, vol. 49, no. 5, pp. 1048–1057, oct. 2002.

[9] R. Beig, u. R. Y. Kumar, and v. T. Ranganathan, “a novel fifteen level inverter for photovoltaic power supply system,” in *conf. Rec. 39th ieee ias annu. Meeting*, 2004, pp. 1165–1171.

[10] Anis w. R analysis of a three-level bridge inverter for photovoltaics, solar cells 1988, vol. 25, n°3, pp. 255-263 (10 ref.).

[11] L. M. Tolbert, f. Z. Peng, and t. G. Habetler, “multilevel converters for large electric drives,” *iee trans. Ind. Appl.*, vol. 35, no. 1, pp. 36–44, jan./feb. 1999.

[12] Jiang you-hua, cao yi-long and gong you-min, a novel topology of hybrid multilevel inverter with minimum number of separated dc sources iee transactions on industrial electronics, vol. 49, no. 4, august 2002 pp 832 838.

[13] Miaosen shen; joseph alan; jin wang; peng fang z.; adams donald j. Comparison of traditional inverters and z-source inverter for fuel cell vehicles iee transactions on power electronics 2007, vol. 22, n°4, pp. 1453-1463.

[14] Demas, l.; meynard, t.a.; foch, h.; gateau, g. Comparative study of multilevel opologies: npc, multicell inverter and smc with igtb icon 02, iee 2002 28th volume 1, issue, 5-8 nov. 2002 vol.1 pp: 828 – 833.

[15] Hosseini, s.h.; almaleki, m a new online optimal controller for 2-cell multicell inverter. Tencon 2004. 2004 iee conference volume d, issue, 21-24 nov. 2004 pp): 85 - 88 vol. 4.

[16] A.k. Al-othman and tamer h. Abdelhamid, elimination of harmonics in multilevel inverters with non-equal dc sources using pso energy conversion and management volume 50, issue 3, March 2009, pages 756-764.

[17] Richardeau, f.; baudesson, ph.; meynard, t failures-tolerance and remedial strategies of a pwm multicellinverter. Power electronics specialists conference, 2000. Pesc 00. 2000 iee 31st annual volume 2, issue, 2000 page(s):649 - 654 vol.2.

[18] F. Richardeau, p. Baudesson, t. Meynard and c. Turpin fail-safe capability of a high voltage igtb inverter source eur. Phys. J. Ap 15, 189-198 (2001).

[19] Lienhardt, a.-m.; gateau, g.; meynard, t.a.stacked multicell converter: digital sliding mode observation of flying capacitor voltages iee- 32nd annual conference on industrial electronics, icon 2006 volume , issue , 6-10 nov. 2006 page(s):2115 – 2120.

[20] Mcgrat, b.p.; meynard, t.a.; gateau, g.; holmes, d.g.optimal modulation of flying capacitor and stacked multicell converters using a state machine decoder power electronics specialists conference, 2005. Pesc apos;05. Ieee 36th volume, issue , 16-16 june 2005 page(s):1671 – 1677.

- [21] K. L. Shi, t. F. Chan, y. K. Wong, s. L. Ho modelling and simulation of the three-phase induction motor using simulink international journal of electrical engineering education; volume 36 issue 2, april 1999, pp 163-172.
- [22] Ragu balanathan, nalin c. Pahalawaththa and udaya d. Annakkage modelling induction motor loads for voltage stability analysis international journal of electrical power & energy systems volume 24, issue 6, august 2002, pages 469-480.